

PREVISION OF CFRP MOISTURE ABSORPTION

FROM DATA ON NEAT RESIN

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Summary

Following Springer, it is assumed that moisture absorption of CFRP depends only on the matrix. Therefore, only the parameters controlling the diffusion of water through the resin need be known if the quantity of water present at any place in the composite is to be calculated at any time.

The purpose of the research program was to evaluate this assumption through a three-step process :

- 1) measurement of the resin diffusion characteristics
- 2) measurement of the CFRP diffusion characteristics along the three principal directions of the material
- 3) comparison of 2) with predictions made on the basis of various models reported earlier using data of step 1)

There is a relative inadequacy of most of the models to account for microstructural inhomogeneities and/or interface diffusivity.

1. Introduction

Moisture diffusion in carbon-fibre reinforced epoxy is generally recognized to be controlled only by the matrix. So the characteristics of the reinforced material can be predicted in theory from simple tests on the resin, and the unique parameter to know is the fibre volume fraction. For transverse diffusion, which is the usual mode of moisture transport across the composite structure, a model accounting for the slowing down effect of the fibres on the moisture progression is required.

Some of the most widely used models have been derived from other fields with attention to diffusion (e.g. from the properties of electrical transport treated by Rayleigh in 1892) but the approach has been renewed recently by using methods of homogenization together with finite difference or finite element methods.

As seen thereafter, predictions by various models often are in strong disagreement with each other. This lack of precision has been nourished up to now by the scarcity of experimental verifications : to verify how accurate are models bounded by the isolated matrix on one hand and by the composite with the maximum packing ratio on the other hand, good materials have to be fabricated in a large range of volume fraction ; now, the up-to-date technology of prepregs, intended for making in the best conditions composites with 60 to 70 % of fibres, does not fall in properly with the exercise.

Our objective was to obtain the experimental data to test some of the most common models through a range of fiber volume fraction wider than it has been satisfied with before.

It should be emphasized from now that the following results all refer to the first absorption of the predried composite with zero moisture content. As a matter of fact, it has been reported in recent studies that there is a progressive change in the resin response when absorption-desorption cycles are performed. This is an essential point as the composite parts are intended to work in a fluctuating environment. An extension to the present study is in progress to determine whether a stabilization or a continuous drift are to be expected for cycling conditions.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and Testing

Water uptake in water at 4 temperatures (40, 60, 70 and 90°C) was followed for two currently used resin systems namely : Narmco 5208, Ciba 914 and the corresponding laminates reinforced with Torayka T300 carbon fibres ; for the latter moulding requirements were modified to cover V_f between 0.4 and 0.7 : high V_f were obtained by adding supplementary bleeder plies to pump out more resin than usual ; low V_f were obtained by stacking plies of neat resin film of the same batch between the prepreg plies.

Figure 1 - Sample geometry and idealized microstructure according to moisture propagation

The unidirectional plates were cut into specimens with geometries appropriate to moisture propagation in one of the three principal directions of the material (Fig. 1) : for diffusion along direction 1 and 2, fabrication of thick plates (10 mm) was required. It must be pointed out that sound composites with extreme V_f are easiest to be moulded as thick plates that as thin ones ; thus, for high and low V_f , some data in the direction 3 (thin plates) were discarded as porosity was disclosed through the micrographic inspection made on each sample. Specimens were carefully machined along thickness to avoid any skin or coating on the surface.

After the specimens had been dried thoroughly (70°C in the presence of dessicant) until they reached a constant weight, they were immersed into thermostated water and weighed periodically (water uptake is proportional to the square root of time). Weight was recorded for a time as long as to have the conditions of application of the Langmuir equations satisfied. Corrections of data for edge effects were made according Springer expressions [1].

2.2. Data Processing

All the absorption curves were analysed according the so-called Langmuir equations which describe water diffusion as resulting from a competition between two mechanisms : the trapping and untrapping of water molecules in the macromolecular network. Dewas [2] demonstrated that this kinetics, suggested initially by Carter and Kibler [3] and Gurtin and Yatomi [4] to account for anomalies frequently observed in the diffusion tests, is more adapted to the carbon/epoxy composites than Fick equation does (Fig. 2a). Four parameters (instead of two for the Fick equation) are now required to describe the diffusion process : in addition to the well-known diffusion coefficient D and the mass of water absorbed at equilibrium M_s , the two Langmuir coefficients γ (probability for trapping per unit time) and β (probability for untrapping per unit time) have to be introduced. Physical signification of the latter parameters is still indefinite at the present time.

Figure 2 - a) Simplified representation according to Fick or Langmuir equations ; b) Langmuir equation fit to experimental data (+)

Practically, the four parameters are computed from experimental points selected in two regions of the absorption curve : in the linear part of the curve at short exposure times and at large values of time far from the knee respectively. Using iteration, values of β and γ are progressively adjusted to match perfectly the computed curve with the experimental one (Fig. 2b). Then D and M_s can be calculated using Langmuir equations [2].

3. Results

3.1. Neat resins

Due to the relatively important quantity of water absorbed by the resin, determination of β and γ can be expected to be of good precision (Table 1). That those parameters look like adjustment coefficients to the experimental plots rather than true physical quantities is made clear when one considers the first two lines of Table 1 taken as an example : an important change in the pairs of values β and γ has no significant effect on D nor Ms and the latter can be viewed as setting forth adequately the diffusion of the 5208 resin at 40°C (even though the cure cycles exhibit a plateau of 1 h/135°C in the first case and 3 h/130°C in the second case). Accordingly, using β and γ of the resin to predict the β and γ of the composite would be likely meaningless.

Table 1. Diffusion parameters of neat resins
(average of three specimens)

NARMCO 5208					
T(°C)	$\beta \times 10^4$ (h ⁻¹)	$\gamma \times 10^4$ (h ⁻¹)	D x 10 ⁵ (cm ² .h ⁻¹)	Ms (%)	REMARKS
40	4.56	1.52	1.01	4.98	cycle 1
	8.01	2.31	1.06	4.78	cycle 2
60	5.63	1.91	2.70	5.44	cycle 1
70	11.82	3.55	4.20	5.48	"
90	13.11	5.31	6.29	6.30	"
cycle 1 : 1 h/135° + 2 h/180°C cycle 2 : 3 h/130° + 3 h/180°C					
CIBA 914					
40	10.60	7.17	1.55	5.21	cycle 1
	5.80	1.57	1.24	6.65	cycle 2
60	8.34	9.15	2.99	7.96	cycle 1
70	16.92	26.47	4.38	8.91	"
90	23.41	4.33	3.18	9.4	"
cycle 1 : 1/2 h/135° + 2 h/180°C cycle 2 : 1 h/175° + 4 h/190°C					

The invariance of D and Ms is important as the cure cycles used to fabricate composites with variable thickness and/or fibre volume fraction cannot be kept away from experiencing slight modifications.

As might be expected when the cure cycle has been deeply changed, D and M_s depend on the state of the resin, i.e. the degree of cure. This is obvious when one looks at high temperature absorption : example of the 914 resin tested in water at 90°C makes it clear in Table 1. D and M_s do strictly characterize only a resin which can be considered stable in the test conditions.

As a partial conclusion, prediction of composite moisture absorption from resin test data is valid on condition that i) elaboration of both types of materials follows thermal ways near to each other and ii) thermal ways result in cured states held to be stable with respect to the testing environment (moisture and temperature). Various methods (DSC, DMA etc...) were used to check the fulfilment of above conditions.

A simple verification of the second condition was made when diffusivity at four temperatures was plotted according to an Arrhenius law : for the 914 resin cured 2 h/ 180°C , diffusivity at 90°C deviates strongly from the otherwise straight line, which denotes an instable material in these conditions thus yielding unserviceable results.

It must be pointed out that M_s depends on the temperature, a trend often ignored by other investigators. It has to be recalled that M_s follows from a calculation, so it used to be higher than the last experimental point.

3.2. Composites

As the fibres strongly upset the diffusion, it is of primary importance to study how variations of V_f affect it ; for sake of clarity, discussion will turn only on tests carried out at 40°C which are representative of other conditions.

3.2.1. Diffusion coefficients. In Table 2 have been collected the diffusion coefficients computed from treatment by Langmuir equations for the three principal directions. They have been standardized with respect to the diffusion coefficient of the resin cured in the same conditions. The standardization allows us to compare our results with literature data based upon a fickian process. In fact, the comparison relates only to D_3 , across the fibres and the plies since this coefficient, which chiefly determines humidity transfer through the structures has formed the subject of many measurements on the thin plates commonly used for testing composite materials.

In Table 2, D_3 is seen to decrease progressively with V_f in the case of T300/5208. The evolution confirms the few values reported so far, e.g. Augl

[5] or Cook [6]. On the other hand there is no correlation for the second material, with unaccountably spreaded values. Incomplete curing of the thin plates used here to measure D_3 could be the source of the erratic behaviour.

D_2 ought to be equivalent to D_3 in theory to obey the models which assume the unidirectional composite to be isotropic transverse. This does not reflect the actual structure of the material, depicted schematically in Fig. 1, where the stacking of plies is still visible, particularly for the low volume fractions : metallographic inspection show planes of resin with less fibres keeping apart planes of V_f higher than the plate average V_f . In the diffusion along direction 2, moisture propagates in both planes in accordance with a parallel mode (cf Fig. 1) when a series mode is consistent

with propagation along 3. Slightly different diffusivities are associated with each of these regimes. For T300/914, there is a normal decrease of D_2 with increasing V_f (thick plates). Values of D_2/D_R for both materials are close to each other except for T300/5208 at the highest V_f (see after).

Table 2. Diffusion parameters of composites at 40°C
(average of 3 specimens)

T300/5208

V_f	D_1/D_R	D_2/D_R	D_3/D_R	D_1/D_2	D_1/D_3
0.48	0.884	0.454	-	1.95	-
0.57	0.836	0.373	0.524(0.59)*	2.24	1.60
0.61	0.904	0.296	0.481(0.63)*	3.05	1.88
0.67	1.174	0.350	0.446(0.65)*	3.35	2.63

$$D_R = 1.035 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$$

*actual V_f of thin plates used for the determination of D_3

T300/914

0.42	0.680	0.465	0.393(0.41)*	1.46	1.73
0.53	0.637	0.359	0.319(0.56)*	1.77	2.00
0.61	0.449	0.235	0.277(0.60)*	1.91	1.62
0.65	0.376	0.161	0.444(0.67)*	2.33	0.85

$$D_R = 1.553 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$$

*actual V_f of thin plates used for the determination of D_3

Strong disparity is noted between both materials when one looks at D_1 parallel to the fibres : when there is a regular decrease with V_f for T300/914, the second material behaves unexpectedly since the diffusivity exceeds the resin diffusivity at high V_f . To explain the fact, sample quality was first questioned: specimens two millimeters thick cut out of thick plates would offer defects taking the shape of pores opened towards the sens of diffusion, thereby increasing the contact area with water. Sill, major defects are precluded to exist in the controlled samples and T300/914, in similar conditions, exhibits an opposite effect. Finally, data of D_2 on samples cut in the same composite blocks do not show any aberrant tendency.

3.2.2. Other results. Results for the three other parameters β , γ and M_s will not be reported in detail. Water content at equilibrium level rigorously corresponds to that can be calculated from the actual weight fraction of resin so that there is no evidence of any quantitative fixation of water that fibres would promote and M_s can be predicted accurately. As for β and γ , there is an extreme dispersion of values as seen before with the resin.

Plotting D_1 , D_2 and D_3 versus temperature gives straight Arrhenius lines for both materials, except for T300/914 at the highest temperature as aforementioned. On the whole, activation energies derived from the Arrhenius curves are lower for T300/914 (7.40 up to 8.81 kcal.mole⁻¹) than they are for T300/5208 (9.58 up to 10.42 kcal.mole⁻¹) and they depend on the direction [7].

4. Discussion

Literature puts forward theoretical models derived from analogies that exist between diffusion and mechanical, electrical or thermal properties of composite materials. Methods of finite differences [5] or, more recently, technics of homogeneization using finite elements [8] have been applied to the problem. Solutions have been derived to describe D as a function of V_f ; they were summarized by Augl and Berger [5], Kondo and Taki [9] etc... All models assume the unidirectional composite as being formed of fibres regularly distributed through the matrix with a square or hexagonal array and only two directions of diffusion. It has been further assumed that, for carbon/epoxy, moisture is absorbed only by the resin.

With a few exceptions [5-6], there was no real attempt to verify these solutions in a broad range of V_f as the authors generally confined themselves to compare the measured diffusivity D_3 for a material of given V_f -about 0.6- to the predicted value.

Here the diffusion coefficients completed from the Langmuir equations differ from Fick's ones by a factor given by equation (1) :

$$D_{\text{Langmuir}}/D_{\text{Fick}} = ((\beta + \gamma)/\beta)^2 \quad (1)$$

but it is feasible to compare directly the standardized coefficients D/D_R .

4.1. Transverse Coefficients D_2 and D_3

Figures 3 and 4 display results of Table 2 for D_2 and D_3 respectively, compared with predictions of four different models.

The original model by Shen and Springer [1] is resumed in equation (2) :

$$D_2/D_R = D_3/D_R = 1 - 2 \sqrt{V_f}/\Pi \quad (2)$$

Still, the thermal analogy used by Springer was reconsidered by Kondo and Taki [9]. The latter introduced in the Fick law the concept of relative moisture concentration C/C_∞ (where C_∞ is the limit concentration at the end of the test) in place of the usual C . The correction leads to a somewhat different expression for $D(V_f)$ equaling to divide (2) by the factor $(1-V_f)$.

Going a pace farther, Kondo and Taki reject the assumption of a regular distribution of fibres, no consistent with the reality. To make allowance for the randomness, the authors put forward to introduce in the constitutive equation another parameter ("degree of randomness") that cannot be computed a priori but can be assessed by fitting to experimental data. In Figs. 3 and 4, the curve presented (taken from [9]) corresponds to a parameter value of 0.5 that Kondo and Taki think to be the best one to depict the random array of actual composites.

Figure 3 - Experimental data compared to theoretical predictions. Transverse coefficient D_2 vs. volume fraction.

Figure 4 - Experimental data compared to theoretical predictions. Transverse coefficient D_3 vs. volume fraction.

A fourth solution, derived by Engrand [8] and crosschecking an analytical expression given by Hashin [10] has been put on the figures.

Though all the models predict a reduction of D when V_f increases, none of them is likely to integrate the various perturbations brought about by the composite microstructure as referred before (see § 3.2.1.).

4.2. Longitudinal Coefficient D_1

Testing along the fibres is of particular interest to verify the assumption that interface does not affect the diffusion process, which is a basic feature of all models. Results are given in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Experimental data compared to theoretical predictions. Longitudinal D_1 vs. volume fraction.

Resorting to the same concept of relative moisture concentration, Kondo and Taki deviate again from the former models and predict that, in direction 1, composite diffusivity equals the matrix diffusivity. This is a completely different view in respect of the classical solution written as :

$$D_1/D_R = 1 - V_f \quad (3)$$

but the point could not be settled by lack of related results : Kaelble [11] was alone to give pertinent data, reporting that $D_1/D_R = 0.515$ for a material of $V_f = 0.6$ at the first absorption and $D_1/D_2 = 2.38$, $D_1/D_3 = 2.57$.

Together with our results of Table 2 where a ratio of about 2 has been found, there is ample evidence to conclude that diffusion along the fibres is faster than across them. Such a difference was reported before for glass-fibre reinforced epoxies (see, for example, Dewimille and Bunsell [12]).

As far as the T300/914 material is concerned, variations of the fibre content clearly affect D_1 , approximating equation (3), but the second material - T300/5208- offers a prominent feature as, for high V_f , D_1 exceeds

D_R , as seen in Table 2. As a first interpretation, an interfacial diffusion might exist for that material, whose contribution does normally increase with V_f ; this interfacial diffusion might be mirrored in the abnormal high D_2 pointed out for high V_f (Table 2). As a general rule, the ratios D_2/D_R are on an average higher for this material than they are for T300/914 whose interface should not display special properties.

Some provisional observations about the compared fatigue properties in shear of both materials [13] can be put together with the above conclusions: when comparing fracture surfaces of broken 10° off axis tensile specimens, it turns out that rupture occurs in the matrix close to the fibre for the dry T300/914 and at the very surface of fibre for the dry T300/5208 (Figure 6). On the other hand, when both materials are saturated with moisture, locus of rupture is the interface in both cases.

Figure 6 - Aspect of broken unidirectional specimens after fatigue testing in shear: T300/914 (left) and T300/5208 (right) both in a dry state.

Hence determination of D_1 would appear to be well appropriate to detect any interfacial diffusion that the current controls (since testing thin plates give only D_3) are unfit to disclose. That could meet recent McKague's recommendations [14] that the effect of sizes upon the moisture absorption of new composite materials has to be carefully investigated.

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References

- [1] C.H. SHEN and G.S. SPRINGER
J. Composite Materials 10 (1976) 2-20
"Moisture absorption and desorption of composite materials"
- [2] J.N. DEWAS
Compte-rendus des Troisièmes Journées Nationales sur les Composites, JNC-3, Paris (1982) 89-96. "Application of the Langmuir's model to water diffusion in epoxy/carbon type composite materials".

- [3] H.G. CARTER and K.G. KIBLER
J. Composite Materials 12 (1978) 118-131. "Langmuir-type model for anomalous moisture diffusion in composite resins".
- [4] M.E. GURTIN and C. YATOMI
J. Composite Materials 13 (1979) 126-130. "On a model for two phase diffusion in composite materials".
- [5] J.M. AUGL and A.E. BERGER
8th SAMPE Tech. Conf. (1976) 383-427. "Moisture effect on carbon fiber epoxy composites".
- [6] T.S. COOK, D.E. WALRATH and P.H. FRANCIS
22nd SAMPE Symp. and Exh. (1977) 339-348. "Moisture absorption in graphite-epoxy composite materials".
- [7] J.P. FAVRE and J.N. DEWAS
Compte-rendus des Quatrièmes Journées Nationales sur les Composites, JNC-4, Paris, (1984) 615-630. "Diffusion of water in carbon epoxy composite materials - Evaluation of a model based on matrix absorption".
- [8] M.C. MERIENNE, D. ENGRAND et J.P. FAVRE
Rapport Technique ONERA 36/7086 (novembre 1982).
- [9] K. KONDO and T. TAKI
J. Composite Materials 16 (1982) 82-93. "Moisture diffusivity of unidirectional composites".
- [10] Z. HASHIN
NASA CR-1974 (mars 1972). "Theory of fiber reinforced materials".
- [11] C.L. LEUNG, P.J. DYNES and D.H. KAEUBLE
ASTM, Special Tech. Publ. 696 (1979) 298-315. "Moisture diffusion analysis of microstructure degradation in graphite/epoxy composites".
- [12] B. DEWIMILLE and A.R. BUNSELL
J. Phys. D : Appl. Phys. 15 (1982) 2079-2091. "The modelling of hydrothermal aging in glass fibre reinforced epoxy composites".
- [13] J.P. FAVRE et G. VIDAL
TEQC 83 - Proceed. Intern. Conf. on Testing, Evaluation and Quality Control of Composites, Guilford (1983) 57-65. "In-plane and interlaminar shear fatigue characterization of unidirectional GFRP and CFRP, including moisture effects".
- [14] L. Mc KAGUE, J. FRUIT and J. REYNOLDS
SAMPE Journal (nov/dec 1979) 6-11. "Tests of graphite-fibre sizing effects upon laminate properties".

